

The Analysis of Teacher Trainees' Multi-modal Discourse in Middle School English Classes

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Abstract

In order to investigate the multi-modal discourse characteristics of excellent teacher trainees in English class, the teaching videos of five first-prize teachers in the final of the National Teaching Skills Competition for Normal College Students were selected as corpus, and the multi-modal discourse analysis framework was integrated for quantitative analysis. The results show that the mode types selected by teachers are basically the same, and teachers all pay attention to the selection of non-language modes. In different teaching stages, the complexity of modes is different. The selection of modes is related to the focus of teaching stages and the complexity of tasks. The teachers of the competition are good at selecting modes to assist teaching. It is suggested that teachers should make full use of multi-modal methods, follow the principle of modes selection and pay attention to the synergistic effect of modes in order to achieve the purpose of improving the classroom teaching effect.

Keywords: English teaching; Teaching Competition; Teacher Trainees; multi-modal Discourse Analysis

1. Introduction

Language plays an indispensable role in reflecting meaning. However, a large part of the meaning in the communication of human being actually conveyed by non-oral factors such as facial expressions, gestures and so on. Those factors are important means and methods of human communication. With the continuous development of information technology, new written language phenomena and new ways of meaning expression have entered our everyday life continually, the multi-modal meaning and the large number of genres have become the new trend of language development.

In this condition, multi-modal Discourse Analysis (MDA) has emerged and received great attention, especially in the application of English teaching area. It is a discursive analytical perspective that sees all modes of communication as resources for meaning construction (Jewitt, 2006). The multi-modal symbol theory, which is studied from the perspective of social semiotics, emerged in the west at the end of the 20th century. In recent years, there has been a large number of researches and rapid development in different fields in this area. With the widespread application of multi-modal method in the process of communication, only focusing on language can no longer meet the needs of teaching. Teachers' expressions, voices, gestures and actions, as well as language, are an integral part of the construction of multi-modal classroom (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2006), which play an indispensable role in classroom communication. Therefore, multi-modal discourse in classroom teaching has also begun to attract attention. With the expansion of the research area, there are already some research in the field of language teaching mode of teaching practice. The discourse multi-modal class requires teachers design their classes according to the specific teaching

content and use reasonable design of pictures, sounds and physical objects, such as video, sounds and activities. They are also required to use facial expressions and body movements to convey information to stimulate the students' senses, and finally stimulate students' interest in learning.

With the increasing emphasis on English education in China, the number of English teachers continues to grow, and a large number of teacher trainees join the team every year. And the improvement of teacher trainees' teaching ability has become an important research topic. Previous studies put forward the improvement direction of teacher trainees by comparing the teaching methods of skilled teachers and teacher trainees. However, the growth of teachers' experience needs time to accumulate, and it is still not enough for teacher trainees who just get touch on teaching practice to improve their ability just rely on the experience of skilled teachers alone. In this case, studying the teaching characteristics of excellent teacher trainees can provide more direct and complementary suggestions for the improvement of the teaching ability of teacher trainees group .

Founded in 2014, the National Teaching Skills Competition for Normal College Students has been successfully held for six times. It is a special teaching competition for Chinese normal university students of various disciplines. The competition aims to exchange training experience of normal university students, promote the improvement of teaching ability of normal university students, and cultivate outstanding teachers with ethics, advanced teaching concepts and skills. The participants of the competition are outstanding normal university students and excellent teacher trainees selected by the education colleges of normal universities and non-normal universities. The abundant classroom teaching samples formed by the teaching competition provide fresh and vivid corpus for the in-depth observation of the multi-modal discourse characteristics in the class of excellent teacher trainees.

From the perspective of multi-modal discourse analysis, this paper intends to conduct a quantitative analysis on the modal types, analyze the modal synergy characteristics of teacher trainees in the teaching competition and explore the characteristics of multi-modal teaching by excellent teacher trainees. This study hopes to provide suggestions to novice English teachers to utilize multi-modal resources in order to facilitate English teaching.

2. Literature Review

Multi-modal discourse and multi-modal discourse analysis

Multi-modal discourse refers to the phenomenon of using various senses such as hearing, vision and touch to communicate through different means and symbolic resources. It is the result of the comprehensive use of human perception channels in the process of communication, and its theoretical basis is Halliday's Systemic Functional language.

In the 1990s, British linguists Kress and Van Leeuwen (1994) put forward a new method of discourse analysis, named the theory as multi-modal discourse analysis, and then led a lot of related research in this area. Kress and Van Leeuwen(1996;2001;2003) study the relationship between modality and medium for several times. They believe that modality is a symbolic resource that implements both discourse and communicative categories simultaneously. Modality can be realized by medium. Their studies provide theoretical basis and research methods for multi-modal discourse analysis. Royce(1998;2002) studies the complementarity of different symbols in multi-modal discourse as well as multi-modal synergies in second language classroom teaching. Cope and Kalantzis (2000) explore the development of multiple modal reading and writing skills. Apart from the systemic functional perspective, O' Halloran (2005) probes into multi-modal discourse and meaning making generated via the interaction of different modes from the perspective of the systemic functional language theory. Other studies (Jewit 2004, Smith 2011) not only studied the theoretical construction of multi-modal, but also specifically studied multi-modal phenomena and multi-modal technology in mathematical discourse and tried to design multi-modal analysis software.

With the advent of the Internet and multimedia era, the theory of multi-modal discourse analysis has attracted attention from many fields due to its strong adaptability and advantages, such as poetry analysis, sculpture research, film appreciation and special purpose corpus analysis.

multi-modal discourse analysis focus on the symbol system other than language, emphasizes the independence and correlation characteristics of these symbols at the same time. It is a phenomenon that uses various senses such as hearing, vision, touch, smell, taste, and movement to communicate through language and other means of symbol resources. According to multi-modal discourse analysis, language is a social symbol, in addition to language, some non-oral symbols and language jointly combinewith each other to construct social meaning. These language modal signs are independent and interactive, studying one of them in isolation cannot fully explain the whole meaning of utterance.

Multi-modal Teaching

Kress & van Leeuwen (2001) study the functions of various symbols including oral and non-oral ones like images, writing, speech, action and body in class, advocating the importance of non-oral modes in class. Jewitt (2002) states that the multi-modal system in the classroom has a considerable effect on teachers' teaching and students' learning. Later in 2006, he takes a multi-modal perspective to examine the impact of technology on learners' literacy and learning. Choi& Yi (2016) examine how two teachers with limited experience with English language learners employ multi-modal methods in their classes. Qualitative analysis of the data show that multi-modal teaching particularly helps learners improve understanding of subject-matter knowledge, allows them to powerfully express what they have learned, and provides them with a psychological refuge. Grapin (2018) presents weak and strong versions of multi-modality from the perspective of learners' leaning. This analysis also shows how the multi-modality reveals the uniqueness and limitations of language, which is a pattern specifically related to English learners.

As for the multi-modal discourse analysis of English teaching in China, Li(2003) comprehensively introduced the theory of multi-modal discourse analysis based on social semiotics. In the following years, scholars successively conducted multi-modal research. Hu(2007) analyzed the difference between multimedia and multi-modal symbols, and discussing the dual characteristics of computer symbols as both modes and media. Zhang (2009) proposed a comprehensive framework of multi-modal discourse analysis, and proposed that multimedia technology should provide teaching scenarios and convenient conditions for teaching, and should serve as tools, assistants and supplements to provide multi-channel expression of discourse meaning for teaching. Then in the field of language teaching, many scholars did their research based on Zhang(2009). Zhang(2012) took college English teachers' classroom discourse as example, did the multi-modal discourse studies based on ELAN. Ding (2017) studied and practiced listening teaching for college English majors from the perspective of multi-modal discourse. Chen(2018) explored the past, present and future of multi-modal discourse research through real and detailed data results based on the visualization analysis conducted by domestic and international core journals. Zhu(2007) points out that all means and media of communication can be regarded as modes, including not only language, but also a series of symbol systems such as sound, image and color. Any discourse involving two or more modes is multi-modal discourse.

Along with the continuous renewal of new media, new technology and development of informationization, intellectualized, already more and more deep into the teaching activities in the field of language teaching, many researchers also means of multi-modal discourse analysis showed strong interest, in view of the multimedia classroom teaching, conducted on vocabulary acquisition, listening comprehension, rate of internalization of learning. If can reasonable use of multi-modal discourse analysis theory, its strong explanatory power and force can not only on the different link of classroom more comprehensive interpretation and analysis, also can attract the attention of the students in class, improve the students' study interest, help them to understand and grasp the learning content, thus improving teachers' and students' classroom experience, achieve better learning effect.

3. Method

The teaching videos of 5 first-prize English contestants in the final of the 6th National Teaching Skills Competition for Normal College Students were selected as the source of corpus. The National Teaching Skills Competition for Normal College Students is held in colleges and universities throughout the country at first, and then the schools next elect outstanding students to participate in the final. Since the career path of normal students is relatively fixed, most of them will become English teachers in different places after graduation, the level of the first prize contestants can represent the level of excellent teacher trainees, and the class discourse of the winners can reflect the multi-modal discourse characteristics of excellent teacher trainees in teaching. The course duration of the competition is 10 minutes, with a complete teaching process and the use of multimedia assisted teaching. The competition is all English reading courses with similar themes, which are comparable.

This study is based on Zhang Delu (2010a)'s framework for modal collaboration and analysis in English classroom teaching. Combined with the actual content of competition videos, modal is divided into two categories: language and non-language. The details are as follows:

Table 1. The framework for modal collaboration in English classroom teaching

Modes	language mode	written language mode	PPT, blackboard, paper materials
		Speech mode	Change of intonation, oral language
	Non-language mode	Visual mode	Pictures, video
		Hearing mode	Songs, recordings
		Postures	Gestures, body movements, facial expressions

In this study, written language and speech are classified as language modes. The written language include blackboard writing, PPT written language and paper materials. Non-language modes include vision, hearing and posture, in which picture belongs to visual mode, and video belongs to visual mode. Sound modes, including songs and recordings, are classified as auditory modes. Actions and objects belong to the mode of body language, and the definition standard of gestures and body movements under the mode of action is that gestures only have hand movements, and body movements include movements of other parts of the body and the movement of the whole body. The times of mode is counted as one time according to the teacher's use of one mode, and it is counted as a second time after using another mode and so on.

The framework for dividing teaching stages in teaching procedures refers to Zhang (2010). And considering that the competition process is a demonstration class and does not include all the stages, six stages of teaching are retained, namely, the beginning of class, the introduction of teaching content, the announcement of teaching purpose, the text understanding, the organization of activities and the summary of the class. By watching the video and recording the use of various modes of each teacher, we hope to answer the following questions through analysis:

A.What are the overall characteristics of multi-modal discourse of teacher trainees and what are the commonalities?

B.What are the characteristics of multi-modal discourse of teacher trainees at different teaching stages in class?

C.How do the teacher trainees select the modes to facilitate their teaching?

4. Results

The characteristics of multi-modal discourse of teacher trainees

In order to answer question A, the teaching videos were each analyzed at least 3 times, the first time is for the counting of written language mode, visual mode and hearing mode, then for speech mode and the last time for postures. And the results are as follows:

Table 2. Number of each mode

CONTESTANTS			No.1	No.2	No.3	No.4	No.5	average
MODES								
language	written language	PPT	3	4	8	7	7	5.8
		blackboard	8	4	1	4	4	5.25
		Paper materials	2	2	7	1	1	2.6
	speech	oral language	107	113	103	119	98	108
		Rising intonation	37	23	20	28	33	28.2
Non -language	visual	pictures	1	1	3	2	2	1.8
		video	0	0	0	1	0	---
	hearing	Songs and recordings	0	1	0	0	0	---
	postures	gestures	40	27	28	37	23	31
		Moving to student	15	8	6	17	23	13.8
		Nodding	17	13	3	8	18	11.8
		Gazing one student	8	6	5	9	9	7.4
		Gazing the blackboard	6	6	2	8	2	4.8
Smiling	7	8	5	6	17	8.6		

It can be seen from the Table that teachers make full use of modal symbol resources such as oral language, eye contact, rising intonation and gestures in the 10-minute class, and the most frequent use is oral language (all around 100 sentences and average 108 in ten minutes) and gestures (23-40 times in 10 minutes). Teachers also use rising intonation frequently in class. Then follow the non-language modes such as moving to students, nodding and smiling.

The modes selected by the five teacher trainees were basically the same. It can be seen that the modal selection of the two teachers in the teaching is mainly the oral language mode. According to the video, teacher trainees use oral language mode in nearly 80% of the time, it was decided by the essence of reading classes that the teacher has to lead

the students to think about the content and meaning of the articles. The number of the sentences which teacher trainees said in the whole class were counted in the data analysis period. It can be found out that the numbers are around 100 and the average number is 108. Teachers tend to use short sentences in class. For one reason, they have to consider the English level of their student. The students are all from middle school and cannot comprehend complex sentences continuously just by listening to their teachers' instruction in reading class. For another, short sentences are more understandable and can provide more information in the fixed time so that they can help student comprehend the passage better in the 10-minute class. The number of the sentences also shows that the teachers speak not so fast. This can help the students understand teachers' instruction and explanation more clearly. The rising intonation is also a point to pay attention to. teacher trainees in the competition tried to use this mode to emphasize important information and highlight key points, such as "right?" "OK?" "can we?". They also use the mode to ask student questions and give students tasks.

Secondly, in the use of non-language modal, all the 5 teachers pay attention to the use of gestures. Teachers use a lot of onomatopoeia and metaphorical gestures to help reduce the difficulty of the task when explaining. At this time, gestures reflect the conceptual and written meaning of the discourse.

The mostly used gestures in the videos is to facilitate the teacher to express his or her idea. They usually reach out their right hand as if they are lifting a small object in hand. This gesture can attract students' attention to teachers' speech and help them focus on the important part of the class.

Another gesture which is used a lot is to let student stand up and answer questions. When using this gesture, teachers would also say "please" at the same time, this is the representation of the interpersonal meaning. Students can feel the respect from their teachers and would be more willing to communicate in the process of learning, and the class would get a better achievement as a result.

It was also be found that the gesture which teachers use to let students sit is also frequently used in classes. This might be the wag in which teacher trainees can set up their prestige, for teacher trainees usually lack of confidence in their early years' of teaching. This gesture would help them remind themselves as a superordinate character and have the confidence to continue their teaching. Gestures reflect interpersonal meaning and improve students' acquisition of conceptual meaning. In addition, when teachers use oral language to explain, they use gesture to coordinate the speed of speech or help students to break sentences, which also reflects interpersonal meaning and written language meaning.

Other postures are also used in the classes. Smiling indicating that teachers attach great importance to providing emotional support to students and paying close attention to students' understanding. When students are asked to answer questions, they are encouraged by the smile of their teachers. It can be noticed that teacher No.5 use smiling much more than others(18times/ 10 minutes), it is more than two times as other teachers. This teacher is a male teacher and is good at conveying positive emotion. In his class, students are much more active than other class, and thus teacher No.5 can create a better atmosphere in his class, students are more willing to communicate with teacher and with each other. Eye contact is the most frequently invoked non-language mode in the course of teaching, which mostly reflects the interpersonal meaning of discourse. For example, when the teacher is explaining, his eyes will gaze the blackboard and, and his eyes can play the role of sending out information and suggest students to look at the blackboard. When the students are answering questions, teachers would gaze at them and give them feedback such as nodding as soon as possible. This would definitely exert positive influence on students' learning effect.

Due to the use of PPT to assist teaching, all the 5 teachers focus on the use of PPT font size, color changes to provide students with multi-modal stimulation, highlight the key points, in order to attract the attention of students. The PPT is used along with the blackboard and paper material. PPT can provide many modes in the class, such as written language, songs and videos. It can also save a large bunch of time as the information could appear in second. The teacher no longer need to waste time to write on the blackboard. However, the overuse of PPT would distract the student to some extent and made them pay less attention on the real content of the class. As a result, the use of blackboard and paper material is necessary. Among the contestant, all the teacher trainees tried to use all these three

kind of written language in their class. However, their using frequency is quite different. Blackboard written language is a good way to help teachers make summary of the class. Those who use blackboard less forget or failed to give a good summary of the whole class, and that's a key point teacher trainees should pay attention to.

In conclusion, it can be seen that language still occupies a dominant position in college English classroom teaching, and other modes facilitate language modes to construct a better class.

The characteristics of multi-modal discourse of teacher trainees at different teaching stages

In each stage of classroom teaching, the choice of modes is not the same. It can be seen that oral language is always the main mode of classroom teaching, which combines through the whole teaching processes together. Here we would use the video of teacher No.3 as an example to find out the The characteristics of multi-modal discourse of teacher trainees at different teaching stages as her using frequency of each mode is close to the average frequency.

The modes used at the beginning of class are quite simple. The teacher's primary mode in the whole class is spoken language. Teacher said "Good morning class, nice to meet you!" and use this mode along with smiling and gestures to create a active beginning of the class. In the stage of the introduction of teaching content, the teacher trainees use the role playing method to pretend as a tourist. In this stage, the written language become the mostly used mode, teacher handed out the paper material she made herself and also used the PPT to give the role playing a background. This method increases the interest of the course and also increases the interest of the students. In this stage, language, gesture and facial expression are also used. And by setting the scenario as going to a tour, the teacher trainees introduce the teaching content which is about the rain forest in America. In the stage of the announcement of teaching purpose, the teacher trainees used a little game of brainstorming, asked the students what they thought of when they heard of rainforest. By doing this game, she announce the teaching purpose which is learn about the rainforest introduce by the passage and improve the reading ability. In this stage, PPT was used frequently in visual, hearing and written language mode, the picture of forest is showed on the screen and there are also sounds of forest when the written language appear on the screen. That is the use of multimedia to facilitate the teaching method and could give more direct introduction to the students.

In the stage of the written language understanding and the organization of activities, there exist the highest modal complexity in the class. Teachers use a lot of oral language to reorganize the written language, and then organize the structure or explain the key language points. The written language carried by PPT assists oral explanation, provides clear and specific information for the article understanding, and improves the modal stimulation effect, and blackboard is also used to provide a frame work of the whole class, and give help to the later stage of the summary of the class. Oral language and written language both play an important role in express the meanings. In the language, the rising intonation and stress of the teacher's explanation highlight the key information, complement and strengthen the language mode, and reflect the meaning of written language. During the questioning, the teacher may scan the class or focus on the individual to figure out whether they understand the student's reaction. Gestures are used to mark key information or to attract students' attention; walking towards students and eye contact with them highlight the advantage of interpersonal communication of multi-modal discourse. And in the process of organizing activities, in addition to using oral language to organize students to discuss the topic, teachers also use different non-linguistic modes. For example, in the process of individual communication with students, teachers' eyes will focus on one or several students to encourage students. By scanning the whole class, the information coverage is expanded to the whole class. In the discussion activities, teachers approach students for close communication, which can make students get more emotional support and promote the enthusiasm of students' discussion. In addition, in the stage of organizing activities, teachers used a lot of gestures, such as gestures to mark the key information in students' opinions and gestures to reduce the difficulty of abstract understanding. The non-language modal selection of the teacher trainees in the stage of organizing activities construct the main part of the class and make the class more attractive to the students.

Then comes to the last stage where teacher give the summary of the class. As it is the demonstration class whose duration is only 10 minutes, the stage of homework assigning which is common in the teaching practice is replace by thinking suggestion in the summary stage. So the last stage in this analysis is the stage of the summary of the whole class. In this stage, teacher use gesture to show students the framework on the blackboard and the suggestion on the screen. And she also use oral language mode to lead the class.

To sum up, all the modes are used all over the stages. However, it can be seen that in the stage of text understanding and activity organization which the teacher trainees lead the class with the highest complexity of teaching tasks, the complexity and frequency of modes selected by teachers are much higher than those in other stages. In the stage of explaining the text knowledge, in order to make students fully understand the teaching content, the teacher uses more oral language to control the class process, uses written language to assist in improving stimulus, accompanied by language font and rising intonation to facilitate the main mode. Teachers scan the class frequently to control the class, obtain information or diffuse information, turn to the screen or focus on the individual to attract students' attention, and reflect meaning of the discourse. In the process of organizing activities, in addition to controlling the progress of the whole class with language modes, teachers also use a large number of eye glances to improve students' participation in activities. They also use gestures to simulate a specific thing or action or to represent abstract things, by which the meaning was fully reflected in the class.

Ways in which teacher trainees select the modes to facilitate their teaching

In the teaching process, in addition to language mode, all the teachers consciously or unconsciously choose a lot of non-language communication mode, such as eye contact, gestures, walking towards the students and smiling. They also use language mode such as rising intonation, written language in PPTs and paper material. multi-modal pattern of classroom teaching are realized, and the coordination of modes are different at the different stages of the classroom teaching.

In the stage of text understanding and organizing activities, which are the two stage of the most abundant using of the modes, the main modes used by the teacher are oral language, written language, intonation, eyes contact (scanning the class, turning to the screen and focusing on the individual) and gestures. The combination and coordination of the modes are also abundant in these two stages. In the text understanding stage, for example, when teacher needs to explains the meaning of the specific sentence, he or she would first presents three sentence in PPT on the screen, asks questions in rising intonation and glances at the students to get information about whether the students are familiar with the words in the sentence. At this time, the teacher use large amount of the oral language and emphasizes the information, he or she would gaze the screen to direct the students' attention to the PPT text. They use written language on PPT to provide complements or reinforces spoken language, with visible hand gestures that indicate the importance of the sentence, by approaching the students teacher observe the reaction of the students and find out where confuse them. They use postures to facilitate the oral language to let students get a more clear understanding. The gesture are used instead of tedious spoken language instructions and nodding affirmation student's answer, immediately turn the eyes to the student further question to show the encouragement to the students. that's all the combination of the modes.

And in the organization activity stage, students become the main part of the class. As a result, teachers' spoken language and written language has largely reduced. Walking towards the students, gestures and eye contact such as scanning the whole class, gazing specific student here to play the communicative role to provide emotional support, also to support the communication between teachers and students.

Classroom activity is to enable learners to comprehensively use the language knowledge and skills learned in this lesson in the set context and complete specific communicative tasks through group activities. Classroom activities have three functions: one is to transform the knowledge and skills learned before into communicative competence, which needs to be realized through practice. The second is to check whether the teaching objectives of this course have been achieved. If the students can successfully complete the communication tasks, it means that they have mastered the

language knowledge and skills of this course and have completed the transformation to language use ability. Third, let the students fully participate in the teaching process, improve the students' interest in learning, show their intelligence and wisdom, and enhance the cooperation and exchange between students. There are various forms of classroom activities. In order to ensure the comprehensive use of the learned knowledge and the participation of students, multi-modal classroom activities are generally selected. However, when organizing multi-modal classroom activities, it is necessary to consider the optimal principle to avoid the chaotic mode, which will affect the classroom management.

First of all, classroom activities should have clear language learning objectives, there should not be activities for the sake of activities. Secondly, attention should be paid to operability, classroom activities should be able to achieve the task under the existing environment and conditions, the target should not be too high, to suit the students' language level. Finally, fun is also important. The activity design should be interesting, can attract the participation of learners, improve the learning enthusiasm of students. Purpose, operability and interest are the principles to be followed in the organization of multi-modal classroom activities.

As a result the combination of all kinds of modes is important in this process, the teacher's intonation and PPT text played a strengthening role to facilitate the oral mode. In the stage of the beginning of the class, the introduction of teaching content, the announcement of teaching purpose and the summary of the class, the use of modes are relatively simple, especially at the beginning of the class, the teacher basically only used oral language to reach the purpose of communication. In the teaching content stage, oral language, text language and pictures carried by PPT were used, accompanied by bold and enlarged fonts, which strengthened the oral language. It can be seen that mode selection is positively correlated with the complexity of teaching tasks. The complexity of tasks in the stage of text understanding and organizing activities is higher, so other modes need to be used. This can not only better convey the meaning, but also help to cultivate students' multi-modal discourse reading ability.

To sum up, in the teaching process, the main mode is language mode. The teacher's oral language occupies a dominant position in the whole classroom discourse and controls the whole speed of the class. The written language and font use in PPTs strengthen the key information of oral language and take use of the multimedia. Gestures not only assist language explanation, mark key information, simulate specific things and actions, but also play a role in organizing teaching instead of language. Non-language modes such as eye contact and expressions can attract students' attention and express their feelings in the process of explanation, so as to optimize language expression. It can be seen that language modes and non-language are combined together to participate in the construction of meaning, making the expression more adequate, conducive to learners' understanding, and effectively improving the teaching effect.

5. Discussion

Attach importance to non-language modes

It has been proved that the language modes such as spoken and written language are still the main modes of English classes, but it is also found that other modes are indispensable in teaching process.

According to the results above, it can be seen that teacher trainees attach much importance to the selection and application of non-language modal resources in the teaching competition. When language modes alone are not enough to clearly express the meaning in teaching, teachers can use some other modes to strengthen or supplement their teaching in order to achieve a better expression of the meaning and make the students to have a better understanding of the discourse.

Teacher trainees in the teaching competition use non-language modal resources frequently, which indicates that they are trying their using non-language modal resources to construct meaning, to provide new content for the main mode, and to supplement or strengthen the meaning of the main mode. This should be the point that every teacher trainees should keep in mind. Facial expressions, gestures, movements and the eye contact can convey meaning in the face to face communication, and once understood by students, they can play an excellent role. In the teaching practice,

the use of non-language modes such as gestures, movements or eye contact can effectively shorten the social distance between teachers and students and can help improve students' willingness to communicate. Therefore, these non-language modes play a very important role in the overall expression of meaning, and sometimes can even cause the change of the overall meaning of discourse. As a small social register, the teaching task cannot be accomplished by language alone. By using non-language modes, teachers can alleviate students' anxiety or other negative emotions in the learning process. For example, the teacher smile and nod to provide encouragement to the students, it's much more better than just say don't worry in the class, for the latter may exert more anxiety to the class and go against to the construction of a pleasant class atmosphere. In this condition, the non-language can not only facilitate the language modes, but also be more effective than the language modes to some extent. Therefore, it is suggested that teacher trainees should try their best to make full use of non-language modes in their classes, in order to fully express their idea on the concepts and written languages and fully convey the interpersonal meanings.

Try to find the appropriate mode in each teaching process

In multi-modal teaching, each teaching process has its teaching objectives and oriented tasks, and the combination of specific teaching methods and modes should be designed for each specific teaching stages. The general principle of modes selection is the optimization principle, including several interrelated principles of efficiency principle, adaptation principle and economic principle (Zhang, 2010).

In this competition, teachers avoid using invalid modes, but only used oral language, eye contact and smile to achieve a good teaching effect. This follows the principle of effectiveness. Oral language mode is the main mode of the competition, but in the text interpretation and activity organization stage, only choosing to use the oral language mode cannot fully realize the teaching effect, thus the teacher trainees follow the principle of adaptation, use rising intonation, eye contact, gestures and other non-language modal to strengthen language modal, highlight the language mode of discourse. The economic principle is reflected in that teachers try their best to achieve the best teaching effect on the premise of simplifying the selection of modal resources, otherwise too many modes will not achieve the desired effect, but will distract students' attention and lead to negative effects.

Therefore, in normal class teaching, teacher trainees should choose appropriate modes and mode combinations according to different teaching stages. This process is not only conducive to realizing the meaning of discourse, but also can add new meaning to the discourse, so as to impress students deeply and improve the teaching effect. Under the guidance of the principle of optimization, teachers should consider which mode or which combination of modes can achieve the best teaching effect, such as oral language and written language combination, oral language and gesture combination, written language and picture combination, etc. Too single or too complex combination will certainly affect the teaching effect. The principle of adaptation indicates that in different stages of classroom teaching, teachers should not only choose the content of discourse, but also choose the way of expression and the intonation of oral language. How can written language such as PPT written language or blackboard writing help oral language to more accurately and clearly convey the meaning of discourse; necessary images, animations, or videos are needed to optimize or enhance language modes, etc. In order to optimize the teaching effect, multi-modal resources should be reasonably allocated according to certain principles to form the best combination among modes.

Pay attention to the synergy of modes

Building upon the importance of individual modes, this study emphasizes that the true power of multi-modal teaching lies in the synergistic interplay between different modes. Mode synergy refers to the process where multiple semiotic resources (verbal and nonverbal) work together in a coordinated and complementary fashion to construct meaning that is richer and more accessible than any single mode could achieve alone. This synergy is not merely additive but often transformative, creating emergent meanings through the integration of perspectives offered by each mode.

The observed teacher trainees demonstrated varying degrees of conscious deployment of synergistic combinations. Crucially, these combinations were often tailored to specific pedagogical moments. Below are more detailed examples illustrating how different modes worked together dynamically in the classroom.

The conceptualization of abstract vocabulary: when explaining the word ecosystem in the context of a rainforest text, one teacher did not rely solely on verbal definition. She synchronized her speech with a pointing gesture directed at a complex diagram on the PPT showing plants, animals, soil, and water interconnected by arrows. Simultaneously, she used a slightly slower speech rate and emphasized stress on key terms. Here, the visual diagram provided the concrete representation, the gesture anchored the spoken concept to the specific visual element, the speech provided the abstract label and definition, and the prosodic features (rate, stress) highlighted critical information. This multi-modal synergy offered multiple entry points for understanding the complex concept.

The method to help comprehension and engagement during questioning: when posing a comprehension question like What might happen if a key species disappears?, a teacher immediately scanned the classroom visually. Upon noticing a hesitant student, he walked closer, maintained eye contact with that student, offered an encouraging smile, and used an open-palmed gesture inviting participation. The initial verbal question and intonation set the task. The gaze scanning monitored understanding and identified a potential need for support. The physical proximity, sustained eye contact, and smile served to reduce anxiety and signal encouragement non-verbally. The inviting gesture reinforced the verbal prompt non-verbally. This synergy aimed not just to elicit an answer but to create a supportive environment conducive to risk-taking.

Reinforcing instructions for group work: when setting up a group discussion, a teacher used clear spoken instructions. She accompanied this with a visual countdown timer displayed on the PPT and a sweeping hand gesture indicating the pairing of students nearby. The verbal mode delivered the core instruction. The visual timer provided a clear, non-intrusive time reference, freeing the teacher from constant verbal reminders. The gesture efficiently and non-verbally directed the physical organization of the task, reinforcing the "in pairs" instruction visually and spatially. The synergy here ensured clarity of task, time management, and physical setup with minimal verbal redundancy.

Effective multi-modal teaching requires teacher trainees to move beyond simply using multiple modes and towards consciously orchestrating them. They need to consider how the selection and combination of modes at any given moment can create synergistic effects that enhance clarity, engagement, comprehension, and the overall communicative effectiveness of the classroom discourse. This orchestration involves understanding the affordances of each mode and how they can best work together to achieve specific pedagogical goals within the flow of the lesson.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, in the use of multi-modal teaching method, teachers should pay attention to the role of non-language modes resources in classroom teaching, follow the principle of modal selection to achieve the best combination of modes and pay attention to the synergy between modes to improve the classroom teaching effect. The quality of classroom teaching depends on the teacher's teaching methods and behavior. The more effective teaching behaviors and the less ineffective teaching behaviors, the better the teaching effect will be. Therefore, when teachers teach in English classes, it does not mean that the more modes they use, the better the teaching effect will be. Many of them may be ineffective teaching behaviors.

Teachers must pay attention to the diversity and change of teaching means, understand the advantages and disadvantages of each mode used, and cooperate the modes according to the specific teaching content. Teachers should distinguish between multimedia and multi-modality. The use of multimedia technology does not mean the realization of multi-modal teaching. Even in the absence of multimedia equipment for teaching, teachers can also use a variety of modes, such as the use of physical objects for teaching, which can mobilize learners' multiple sensory channels, such as vision, touch, smell and taste. However, objectively speaking, a long time of single mode teaching will reduce the interest of teaching, will lead to the distraction of students' attention, and the lost of the enthusiasm of learning. Therefore, teachers need to spend more time on lesson preparation and use multi-modal method to create a vivid and interesting classroom.

Multi-modal research is the product of the development of the information age. With the widespread promotion of multimedia, multi-modal theory will be more and more applied in media, teaching and other fields. In the future development process, there will be more breakthroughs in multi-modal research and more achievements. This study applies the theory of multi-modal discourse analysis to the investigation of the teaching of Chinese listening and speaking as a foreign language in content, hoping to better combine modern computer technology with language teaching research. This study still has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample size is relatively small, focusing only on five first-prize winners from a single competition. While these winners represent high-achieving trainees, a larger and more diverse sample would strengthen the findings. Second, the analysis relied solely on the observation and annotation of teaching videos by the researcher, which, despite careful review, carries inherent subjectivity. Future studies could benefit from using specialized multi-modal annotation software for more precise and reliable coding, potentially involving multiple coders to establish inter-rater reliability. Third, and crucially, this study provides valuable insights into the patterns of multi-modal discourse employed by these teachers, but it lacks direct empirical evidence linking these observed multi-modal strategies to student outcomes. The analysis demonstrates what modes were used and how they were combined (synergy), but it does not measure the impact of these strategies on student engagement, comprehension, or learning gains within these specific classes. Therefore, future research should prioritize incorporating complementary data sources, such as post-lesson student surveys or interviews to gauge students' perceptions of the clarity, engagement level, and helpfulness of different multi-modal techniques; measures of comprehension or learning like pre- and post-tests, quizzes, or analysis of student responses and discussions to assess whether specific multi-modal strategies correlate with improved understanding; and systematic observational data on student behaviors during phases where different multi-modal combinations are employed. Such empirical validation is essential to move beyond descriptive patterns and demonstrate the tangible pedagogical benefits of effective multi-modal discourse and synergy in the secondary English classroom. Future research should also explore the application of these findings in real-world, non-competition classroom settings over extended periods.

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